

PERFORMANCE INCREASE BASED ON JOB ANALYSIS WITH COMPETENCY APPROACH ASSIGNED TO MANUFACTURING INDUSTRY 4.0+5.0

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Abstract

Purpose – *The aim of the research topic is to identify a model for increasing performance through the development of human resource competencies in manufacturing organizations, based on the premise that the main needs of employees are related to the training and development of skills as well as the acquisition of knowledge needed within the organization.*

Methodology/approach - *Concepts and theories related to Industry 4.0-5.0 are still new and yet developing, based on empirical studies, which do not work always across the board. For this reason, the research methodology is based on recent literature review and primary data collection from articles published in the last 7-8 years. In parallel, we have also drawn on established formal theories of human resource management, in particular performance management and the recent concept of HPWS (human performance work system). Regarding the theories of the socio-technical system, which define the organization of production, the concepts of W.P. Newman were chosen, because from an ontological point of view they point to the actual reality, versus the old concept of Davis and Trist. The proposed model for determining the growth of human resources performance in the organization is based on the hypothesis of existing of the interaction between the organization as a socio-technical system (based on the theories developed by W.P. Newman) with the categories of employees, who are determined to perform, due to motivational factors, personal skills and the work environment, according to the HRM concepts of Snell & Morris. The technical factors that features Industry 4.0 can boost the enterprise in the race for competitive advantage and can be customized as sources of working tools according to the nature of the activities to stimulate internal human resources. A second hypothesis deriving from the first one is following the main directions of the 4.0-5.0 core competencies as a base of performance of the specialist-operator. The essential competences of the job should be combined with the 10 categories outlined by the World Manufacturing Forum, in 2019 to become the needed mix for a specialist I4.0. Their mix can be different depending on the manufacturing profile, the weight of each competence being determined by the measurement tools used for assesment . This study is proposed to illustrate an example related to the clothing industry by using the job analysis in the organization, having an outcome with job design based on competences based approach of Snell & Morris.*

Findings – *Industry 4.0 -5.0 factors can be a source of learning, in order to obtain the adequate set of competences adapted to the manufacturing industry. Increasing the individual and team performance of employees is based on the development of the 4.0-5.0 competences mix, developing the theory of mass customization at the level of incentive factors which stimulate the contribution of each employee through their particular skills and developed knowledge. Thus, Industry 4.0 factors become the opportunity to grow the organization and win the race for competitive advantage, but a adequate design of job profile must be constructed in order to appreciate and reward specifically the competences which are providing the employees performance.*

Research limitations/implications – *Today, due to the economic crisis triggered by the health effects of the Covid 19 pandemic, there is a steady decline in interest in manufacturing activities, particularly in the garment industry, due to the long training cycle of manual dexterity skills, in which human-machine interaction is predominantly manual, and on the other hand the limited level of computerized development, with managerial preoccupation focused on obtaining profit with reduced personnel costs, without a defined goal linked to the motivation of employees or the attraction of new generations and without the visibility of a personal development perspective. The effervescence of innovations coming from Industry 4.0, besides the obvious advantages offered by technologies, has however led to a lack of focus on the development of human initiative, leadership training and management adapted to the new*

challenges. The definition of Industry 5.0 can be considered as a natural consequence of the unresolved aspects of the Industry 4.0 stage and can be seen as an opportunity to develop the scientific framework to define concepts from the social sciences and humanities with a focus on the human factor.

Practical implications – The major concern is related to the achievement of competences & skills mix for employees, in order to create the level of attractiveness to work in manufacturing production activities. Under these circumstances, the category of human resources that needs attention is related to direct blue collar" human operators with machine interaction. They have to cope with possible job losses through replacement by new means of work Industry 4.0 (cyber-physical system, digital twin, industrial robots) but on the other hand, enterprises are facing acute labor shortages due to outdated human resource management strategies, still lagging behind at the mass production stage of Industry 2.0-3.0. For social & human sciences is unfolding directions of performance research and concepts looking for updated incentive factors to motivate and attract the human resources for manufacturing industry. The proposed model for determining the growth of human resources performance in the organization is based on the premise of existing of the interaction between the organization as a socio-technical system based on the theories developed by W.P. Newman (2020) with the categories of human resources. The employees are determined to perform, due to motivational factors, personal skills and the work environment, aiming to attain the parameters of HPWS (high performance work system) based on human resources management concepts of Snell & Morris (2020).

Originality/value – A research objective regarding management strategies to gather and revise the strengths & weakness of existing practices, in order to turn them into a valuable tool to combat negative effects of volatile/uncertain economic environment.

The work experience of enterprises which succeeded to survive during the pandemic crisis shall be used as best practice examples, to build new direction of human performance researches, available for broad spectrum of industrial activities, not only in the IT industry niche.

Key words: Sociotechnical system Industry 4.0 W.P. Newman, High performance work system Snell & Morris, competences of specialist I.4.0.

Introduction

In view of the new challenges facing the strategic management of organizations that are acutely confronted with staff shortages, competition in the labour market and the attractiveness of activities for their own employees, it was considered relevant to combine the meanings of the human performance in order to take into account efficiency, fairness in the attitude towards people from within, the needed competences to stimulate in the achievement of the purpose of the enterprise, and economic success in caring for competitive advantage and external customers satisfaction. This approach could be confirmed by the matrix model proposed by G.A. Cole (2000) which advance the idea of the link between the level of concern for the customer and the level of concern for the employee, as shown in Figure 1. The human resources management strategies should find the break even point between the quadrants assigned to maximum commitment of to the goal of excellent customer service and satisfaction neglecting the needs of employees and the one of full attention to employees needs. The balance is obtained whenever the chances of achieving a favourable outcome increase, where internal staff is motivated and empowered by the mission. For personnel management, the danger is that it can over-emphasize the needs of employees to the detriment of the customer's cause and miss the ultimate objective of the work and the mission of the organization, which is win-win business operation for the customer and the entrepreneur. Balanced attention to both stakeholder groups increases the chances of success of the whole organisation. Employees expect from management the facilitation of pay entitlements, extrinsic and intrinsic rewards, resolution of internal conflicts, equitable opportunities for promotion and personal development in the context of complex technological challenges in stage 4. 0/5.0. On the other hand, customers and suppliers will exert indirect pressure on human resources management by making the final results of the services provided more efficient and by being more solicitous and serious in communication.

Figure 1. Matrix model diagram of concern level towards internal human resources needs and external customers goals. Source G.A.Cole (2000)

Thus, the human resources management activities in a production organization, particularized on the manufacturing sector of the garment industry, have not changed in the actual circumstances of the new industrial revolution, observed to the existing status in Romanian companies. They start from the idea of group management and management based on objectives at the level of the organization, under the conditions of minimal expenditure on personnel. Taylorist efficiency is active both at the level of "white collars" and "blue collars". At the same time new concepts and operating principles of the industrial technological wave based on IOT(Internet of things), AI (artificial intelligence), cyber entities, industrial robots and cloud databases require new personnel policies and procedures on the issue of upgrading existing staff to learn on the job. For strategic level managers, but especially for line managers, involved in solving operational tasks, a parallel responsibility is related to the personnel tasks, with the complete typical human resource management activities, especially for production operators as follows:

- Selection of human resources;
- Induction & integration of apprentices;
- Professional training on specific jobs and production operations;
- Periodical performance measurement and assessment of employees;
- Staff structuring upon specific jobs;
- Policy implementation referring to internal discipline rules;
- Policy implementation and control the compensation & rewards system;
- Team motivation;
- Set-up of adequate communication channels;
- Safe & security regulation implementation;
- Action plans to facilitate the company objectives implementation; as for example, a new IT platform and system set-up need a project management assignment with detailed measures directed to each work department involved;

All these tasks are complex and need to be undertaken in combination with other activities or specific projects related to operational flow, material assurance, IT equipment or budgeting. In this respect, the HR/personnel departments through their specialists can provide support and specific actions, as follows:

- Establish the HR strategies, on long terms, taking into account to innovate and use the technological facilities offered by the Industry 4.0 entities;
- Consultancy and profiled services exemplified by the needed documents of contracts, job description design, job analysis and design, job profiles;
- Undertaking the operational tasks of recruiting, selection, induction and initial training on the job, assigned to either specialists or instructors.

In view of the changes brought about by the phenomenon of digitization, IOT, or AI, in which most of these activities can be automated, and especially in conditions of a degree of automation of processes and the expansion of industrial robots assisted or not by human staff, the question arises whether and how much of the bureaucratic staff is necessary. Imperatively, the category of consultants and personnel managers is entering a new framework of action and role playing, due to the changes that may occur in job descriptions, the way of performance evaluation for semi-automated or robot-assisted industrial processes, as well as the continuity of training topics and methods, which require IT specialists, innovative technicians and qualified engineers, permanently connected to technological changes. Therefore the new profiles and communication facilities brought by Industry 4.0 demand customized competencies upgrading the job profiles. Consequently, the entire process of HR management requires a complete revision of all the activities starting with selection & recruiting the personnel and particular approach for the manufacturing operations related to:

- Induction of new employees, keeping in mind the actual lack of attractiveness of routine or time investment for skilled or manual productive activities. This is confirmed by the research and paradigm issued by Schoenhals (2021) who identified the perception of coercion determined by regular, mandatory or not audience recognized tasks
- Training methods and career development to stimulate the transformation into a HPWS (high performance work system) which is based on the features of egalitarianism & engagement, shared information & trust, knowledge development, performance reward linkage (Snell, Morris, 2019);
- Updating performance management system of measuring the results, in order to lead towards a fair and motivating system of rewarding human resources, taking into account besides the organisation's objectives, mostly the measurement of competencies which are created inside the company. They could become more visible working to fulfill the need of recognition of people. This is an immediate consequence of mass customization feature of actual industrial revolution. It is not just a market demand, it is a reflection on each individual who needs to feel the consideration for his particular contribution.

Research problem

Looking at the evolution of means of production and technological facilities, it becomes obvious the discrepancy between the technical progress and lack of updating of HR managerial tools to develop the human resources becoming interested in industrial manufacturing jobs. The main feature of production entity within the actual industrial is the SMART FACTORY demanding SMART employees. The candidates shall be attracted by using SMART persuasive managerial strategies, capable to convince them that their future jobs are important and useful both for them and for the organization.

They could be exemplified on a case study representation concerning a profile of premium clothing production organization operating in Romania, representative in terms of credible and stable position on the market. The permanent company concern was related to training and maintaining a skilled workforce, modern technology to determine high level of quality and professional services for clients creating profit. The organization has successfully overcome the extremely difficult period of the Covid 19 health crisis, despite losses and shrinking demand specifically for premium clothing and maintaining top positions as market leaders in their products. For reasons of confidentiality, no names or other particulars of recognition of the enterprise will be specified.

The study takes into account the organization structure and HR managerial practices. The function-based structure is specialised by assigning activities and responsibilities to a common function. As a result, all production matters are unified under the control of a production manager, or technical manager, and HR & personnel matters are the primary responsibility of the personnel manager. Specialisation by function gives employees throughout the hierarchy the opportunity to work towards a common goal. This

type of structure allows the accumulation of experience on a particular level of activity, encouraging specialists know-how through on-the-job learning and the exercise of management by objectives. One of the main characteristics is that line relationships through direct supervision over subordinate employees derive from both the operational and managerial chain. Senior function managers have authority over both line employees and those in their own functional areas. A manager involved in HRM (human resources management), such as a HR department manager, is recognized as a position by all levels of operations, along with those in the department that provides direct service to personnel activities such as payroll, document management, employment contracts, etc. He or she has the same level of position in the hierarchy of the organizational structure as other operational or functional level managers. This type of structure provides several advantages to the organization such as:

- employees are grouped according to technical job components or specialties;
- the assignment of employees with profiled skills is facilitated;
- predictable promotion paths are created within the organisation;
- control of activities is centralised at function level;

On the other hand, there are some aspects that are considered disadvantages from HRM's point of view:

- -qualifying by function tends to encourage fragmented group interests, different from those of the organization;
- -difficulty of adaptation and low flexibility, due to the centralisation of functions which creates strong managerial positions on specialised functions and imposes more formalised communication relationships between departments, often competing with reporting to strategic management.

Methodology approach

Concepts and theories related to Industry 4.0-5.0 are still new and yet developing, based on empirical studies, which do not work always across the board. For this reason, the research methodology is based on recent literature review and primary data collection from articles published in the last 7-8 years.

In parallel, we have also drawn on established formal theories of human resource management, in particular performance management and the recent concept of HPWS (human performance work system).

Regarding the theories of the socio-technical system, which define the organization of production, the concepts of W.P. Newman were chosen, because from an ontological point of view they point to the actual reality, versus the old concept of Davis and Trist. Upon a brief review of conclusions obtained by WRU (work research unit) in Great Britain, the job content approach shall be related to the following principles:

- activities must ensure a certain diversity of work pace, methods and skill level;
- activities must allow for feedback on employee performance;
- activities must allow a certain degree of freedom of action;
- work positions and work organisation must provide opportunities for learning and development
- jobs must provide prospects for the future;
- objectives must be clear and ensure the opportunity to participate in decisions on the positions filled;
- the job holders must have at their disposal all the resources appropriate to the activity carried out;
- employee relations procedures must be agreed between management and employees;
- remuneration systems must be designed in a fair way, in relation to the contribution made;
- personnel policies must be fair and appropriate;
- physical conditions of the working environment must be of reasonable quality.

The traditional concept of scientific management of Taylor (1911) still functional on most of manufacturing production organizations is not effective any longer, as it is proved by the actual labor market affected by scarcity of work human power. Staff fluctuation, absenteeism, lack of interest and poor retention of the workforce are some examples of the long-term failure of the concept, which is strongly reflected in the current staff turnover, disinterested in the routine, monotonous work still prevalent in manufacturing garmenting companies. The positive aspects of clear measurability of performance through knowledge of the objective and the possibility for the employee to have feedback by measuring the outcome of the work need to be maintained, the other features needing change.

This study proposed the five concepts of W.P.Newman to approach the work station design in order to improve the performance and four principles of HPWS-Snell & Morris to improve the human labour performance by adding new competencies Industry 4.0 to the specific of core profile. The key concepts W.P.Newman are briefly iterated below, recognized for the latest impact on SSH(social science and humanities).

A.1. Key concept 1 W.P.Newman (2020): "Industry 4.0 systems are socio-technical systems", because all work system are assumed to include social(human) and technical(machine) elements. W.P.Newman argued that" there are no I4.0 systems that do not engage humans across the life cycle in designing, installing, maintaining and operating". Attention to the demand on the people performing these tasks is therefore a design requirement.

A.2. Key concept 2 W.P.Newman (2020): "Attention to HF(human factor) must occur throughout design.The lowest cost and maximum opportunity with the best cost-benefit results come from considering HF from the earliest stages and then throughout design project".

A.3. Key concept 3 W.P.Newman (2020): "Human system interaction engage perceptual,cognitive and motor systems .For this reason,I4.0 system designers must ensure that the demands of their design are matched with human sensory, cognitive and motor capabilities or they risk negative outcome for the human or for the sociotechnical system as a whole.

A.4. Key concept 4 W.P.Newman (2020): "People have psychosocial needs. If I4.0 technologies are used to provide automated performance monitoring and enforcement of employees working to a defined pace,then one might hypothesize that employee's sense of control and job autonomy at work will decline and overall psychosocial profile will shift towards the high strain associated with negative outcome".

A.5. Key concept 5 W.P.Newman (2020): "Organizations tend to" drift to unsafe states... which explain, why industrial revolutions or fads like lean system have been seen as contribution to occupational injuries, accidents and deaths. If I4.0 innovations are to try and break this pattern, then system approach to apply HF in design is needed."

Upon the above iteration and applying to our case study from manufacturing industry, several examples are matching the key concept one, three, four and five. Most of the organizations make changes into the system thinking to the shareholders benefits more and then trying to fit to existing and future capabilities of labor force. For instance, an IT system collecting data from work stations which has not instructions translated for the operators, risk to fail if is not well explained to the working team. Also if there is any automate machine installed which oblige the operator to a faster pace from the first working day could jeopardize the policy of automatization concept. Besides, the reward system shall be motivating the operators who are going to be transferred to a new cutting edge machines, not only by changing the target of performance, but fairness in appreciating the efforts who are made to adapt and learn new techniques. Hence, approaching I4.0 from technology driven approach perspective falls short of systematic consideration of HF(human factor),which is vital needed.

The other approach of methodology provided by literature review is represented by HPWS concept with its particular parameters providing relevant points to develop a model solution for creating the interaction between an organization and potential labor force (human resources) based on common goal.Once the interaction is obtained, this is resulting into a performance which could be increased as much as the elements of HPWS are introduced into the sociotechnical system of organization. Herein a brief list of the main parameters of HPWS summarized from the book of Snell and Morris(2019) regarding the management of human resources:

B.1.-Egalitarianism and engagement: represent the principle of inclusion, people want a sense that they are members, not just workers, in a organization. Moving power downwards in organizations

empowering employees which could be obtained through job enlargement, enrichment and self-managing work teams(Snell,Morris,2019);

B.2-Shared information and trust: when employees are given timely information about the nature of their own work, business performance and strategies, they are more likely to make good suggestions for improvement and cooperation in major organizational change(Snell,Morris,2019);

B.3-Knowledge development: represent the shift from touch labor to knowledge work. Because of the dynamic and fast pace of technical change, knowledge and skill requirements must also change rapidly,with continuous learning(Snell,Morris,2019);

B.4-Performance reward linkage: when companies reward their employees based on their performance, workers are naturally pursue outcomes that are mutually beneficial to themselves. Often include group and organizational incentive pay and even skill based pay.

Approaching the inductive methodology of research, by collecting data from a part of the literature studied confirms the experiences of the real situations encountered. The statistical data found in the work of H.G.Adamkova (2020) show that the lack of attractiveness of the current positions offered in the field of industrial manufacturing production is determined by the fear of lack of job satisfaction and the possibility of achieving the required performance. Based on the mentioned studies and concepts, the actual research developed two assumptions as follows:

- Hypothesis no.one states the achieving performance through the organization's interaction as sociotechnical system with human resources, if human resources are motivated by work attractivity.
- Hypothesis no. two complements the previous statements, rationing the performance is based mainly on competences which human resource management practices should take into account the job analysis and job design stages,using the competency-based approach adapted to the Industry 4.0 stage.

The next step of deductive approach is targeting the exhibition of hypothesis, using the interpretative philosophy applied onto the concepts of HPWS upon Snell et All (2018) W.P. Newman (2018),the studies of Agola (2018) related to motivation of human resources, management practices within "smart factory" organizations of Industry 4.0 of Shamim(2016) and Sima (2020). They are illustrated first, onto figure no.2 under the title of performance model as a result of interaction between human resource-organization as sociotechnical system I.4.0.

The organization needs performance to achieve competitive advantage facilitated by technological factors Industry 4.0+5.0. with its transformation into "Smart factory"(Anouk ten Bulte, 2020) or if viewed as a socio-technical system from the perspective of the five concepts W.P. Newman. The human resources component attracted to the organization will interact with the organization as a socio-technical system being interested in meeting performance conditions (Snell, Morris, 2020). Performance, as a result of the interaction between the organization and human resources can increase, fulfilling the High Performance Work System conditions defined by Snell & Morris (2020), thanks to the technological factors of the Industry 4.0 work environment and the appropriate people management practices.

Figure 2. Performance model as interaction result between HR-organization as socio-technical system I.4.0

The exposition of hypothesis no.two is illustrated in the diagram of figure no.3, taking into account that at the basis of performance in the new context of the industrial revolution are the competences formed in the "Smart factory" type organization, defined after the job design &analysis.

Figure 3. Job design HR I.4.0 based on competency based approach

The organization's offer to attract human resources for performance depends on job analysis and job design, as presented in the statistical data provided by H.G. Adamkova (2020) for ensuring job satisfaction. Starting from the assumption that performance is based on the formation of competences, these can correspond to the type of HPWS (high performance work system) approach that combines the essential competences of the specific productive activity with the general competences proposed by the World forum of Work in 2019, characteristic of the 4.0+5.0 industrial phase. The competency-based job analysis approach resulting in appropriate job design (Snell & Morris) can be further developed by introducing the Industry 4.0 competency matrix as proposed onto the research of next chapter and the competency-based reward system, shown in figure no.3.

Findings

Over the last decade, since the declared moment of the Digital Revolution 4.0, the technological transformations that have taken place in the industrial field have led to the effect of "technological determinism", with unpopular effects among employees threatened by job losses due to replacement by robots, on the other hand, in industrial manufacturing sectors such as textile and garmenting production, the negative effects have already been recorded, especially in the pandemic period, through the closure of less modernized industrial units, due to outdated communication systems. In their case, it was not the modernization of industrial equipment that was the cause, but flexibility to change and lack of jobs attractivity, which required speed of reaction in the internal communication process, control of information and speed of decision-making, as well as the precariousness of the IT system based on redundant procedures (manual checking of data entered into the system or input errors). These observed phenomena led small and medium factories to fall behind in the competition for customers, losing their competitive advantage, besides the interest of potential manufacturing operators related to the essential activity of productive process. The technical factors that features Industry 4.0 can boost the enterprise in the race for competitive advantage and can be customized as sources of working tools according to the nature of the activities to stimulate internal human resources.

The winning players that have survived have been those that have constantly invested in re-technologization both in equipping the flow of productive assets, but especially in support and management assets, thus allowing faster reaction speed to environmental phenomena, in order to take managerial decisions of change, restructuring and retraining of the workforce, this field being naturally dependent on the human workforce. The Industry 5.0 stage, by recognising the exaggerated "digitise or dye" elements of the 4.0 stage, is characterised by a focus on the social element, the skilled and flexible human workforce, in order to gain the advantages of digital technology components and to combat the threats already recognised and demonstrated by SSH scholarly research of Ozdemir et al. (2018) as the four assimetries I.4.0. In this case, the change phenomena imposed by the Industry.4.0-5.0 wave requires a greater contact with the outside of the organisation, in order to understand and adapt to new dynamic, linked to the growth of digital skills and technologies on the market. At the same time, a greater focus is needed on the core of middle management and specialists to serve the needs of qualification, training and possible retraining, in order to build occupational profiles adapted to the new requirements of Industry 4.0-5.0, through the HPWS job design of job enrichment, empowerment and professional motivation of employees. The changes being rapid and dynamic, proved by the researches results of SSH, all components of the HR profile must be "on alert", to possible opportunities that may be proposed to strategic management to improve the internal organisational environment and ensure success. Current data, especially after the worsening of the health crisis, which has hit hard the Romanian garment industry (with Covid lockdown for non-essential products), indicate the downfall of organisations that have hesitated to encourage the initiative of specialists and have delayed introducing IT systems for real-time control and monitoring in support of management, rather than looking for strategies of replacing the operators personnel. The last one has been proved to be non-lucrative for the organizations which need qualified resources, especially related to dexterity and skillful operations in production. The actual research is focused on designing the needed job profile for the category of productive direct workers who are not any longer simple executors and shall be interested into a practical, but more attractive content. The performance of a manufacturing organization is based on the efficiency of this category of practitioners whose competencies and abilities for their essential work shall be combined with those outlined by the World Forum of Work in 2019, called here as ten essential qualifications of a specialist I.4.0/5.0, as presented on the figure no. 4.

Figure 4. Essential qualifications of specialist Industry 5.0. Source *World Manufacturing forum* (2019)

The enclosed table no.1 show the summary of core matrix competences needed for apparel factory used as case study for their activities. It can be seen that they are separated into skills or abilities codified with letter “A” and competences codified with letter “C”. According to the subsumed characteristics, skills (aptitudes) are generally related to inclinations, talents, which cannot be learned through education, but can be developed through experience and training. In the case of competences, they are formed through a process of formal, experiential training.

Table no.1-Summary of core matrix competences needed for apparel factory core activities

Activities	Abilities: precision +speed: PA1	Abilities: versatility+precision: PA2	Competence: analytical, organizing, com- munication: PC3	Competence: technical expertise, research: PC4	Competence: creative PC5
Essentials Production:	5	5			
Tehchnical/devel- opment		3	5	5	5
IT:			5	5	4
Marketing, Comercial			5	4	4
Financial			5		
HR			5	5	3
Scale: 1-minimum 5-maximum					

Separately, the same activities are analyzed to see the adequate matrix of which from the ten qualification I.4.0 could be suitable for an upgraded operator I4.0/5.0 into a manufacturing production job, beside the core competences. The data of research are presented onto the enclosed table no.2 entitled as matrix competences I4.0 for a manufacturing organization. Their mix can be different depending on the manufacturing profile, the weight of each competence being determined by the measurement tools used for assessment. Further, this study is proposed to illustrate an example related

to the clothing industry by using the job analysis in the organization, having an outcome with job design on competency-based approach (Snell & Morris).

Table no.2-Matrix competences I.4.0 for an upgraded operator I.4.0 into a manufacturing job

Activities	Essential qualification of specialist Industry5.0									
	#1C	#2A	#3C	#4A	#5C	#6C	#7A	#8A	#9C	#10C
Essentials Production:					5			5	5	5
Technical/development					1-5x			1-5x	1-5x	1-5x
IT:			1-5x		1-5x	1-5x		1-5x	1-5x	1-5x
Marketing, Comercial			1-5x		1-5x	1-5x		1-5x	1-5x	1-5x
Financial	1-5x	1-5x	1-5x		1-5x	1-5x		1-5x	1-5x	1-5x
HR	1-5x	1-5x	1-5x		1-5x	1-5x		1-5x	1-5x	1-5x
Scale: 1-minimum 5-maximum	1-5x	1-5x	1-5x	1-5x	1-5x	1-5x	1-5x	1-5x	1-5x	1-5x
Total	2x(1-5)	2x(1-5)	4x(1-5)		6x(1-5)	4x(1-5)		6x(1-5)	6x(1-5)	6x(1-5)

An example of an Industry 4.0 operator job design based on appropriate Industry 4.0 competencies, to which a competency-based reward system is applied, is shown in Table 3. The score used for the competency assessment is used to establish the appropriate reward system grid for motivating newly developed competency levels.

Table no.3- Job design upon matrix of competences I.4.0 approach

Competency matrix Employee 4.0:		Job design Operator I.4.0 element of:	Job design Operator I.4.0 element of:	Job design Operator I.4.0 element of:	Job design Operator I.4.0 element of:
Competences mix Operator=specialist 4.0	Scale measuring the cumulative competences for reward system: 1-5 (1-minim,5-maximum)	Ergonomic	Engineering	Enrichment	Empowerment
Essential for production: PA1: Abilities of precision +speed:	1-5	-wokstation height adjustment	-learning curves setting to monitor the performance progress	-SMART targets are defined to be attained based on the competencies matrix	-allow the operator's autonomy
Essential for production: PA2: Versatility+precision	1-5	-machine pace to be tunned together with worker natural movement,avoid fatigue of eyes and body	-design and organize the work station upons 5S system		-public recognition by the team
Essential I5.0(5C): Abilities to work physically and pshichologically safely with new tehcnology	5	-translate instruction and set-up of native language for machine programming	-assign a coach/trainer		-possible promotion for recognized position as trainer for the other co-workers
Generale I.4.0(8A): Ability to handle increasing complexity of simultaneous and various tasks	5				
Generale I.4.0(9C): Effective communication skills with the team and other entities of AI,IT	5				
Generale I.4.(10C): Open mindless toward constant change, knowledge transfer from other domains	5				

Verification of the applicability of the competency-based performance model is proposed to be measured through several case studies, at the level of operators in a manufacturing industry, using the competency matrix I4.0, with a correlated reward system. The job design is taking into account as well the elements of HPWS as enrichment, empowerment, ergonomics and engineering of the activity and workstation. The assessment is done with a mix of quantitative and qualitative evaluation based on results and behaviors, adapting the model proposed by Avasilcai and Hutu(2011).

The examples are intended for the category of operators equal specialist I.4.0 as follows:

- for the case of a multi-skilled specialist with a 25-points score of competences of skill mix shown on Table 4;
- for the case of an operator benefiting from improved technology, by automating the equipment with a 19 points score of competences of skill mix shown on Table 5.

In both cases the performance results are rewarded on the basis of competences acquired and optimized over time, which are evaluated based on the scale score shown onto table 4 and 5. Each point can be quantified with a certain monetary value either in Euro or Ron, established by the organization's management according to its own rentability break-even point and profit margins.

Research limitation

The study is still under development for more practical applicable activities. For the moment shall be recognized the existing limitations which are represented by small base of examples provided by one manufacturing industry as apparel & clothing production. On the other hand, this field of activity is enough representative because the labor human factor is the main element to provide performance for the company.

The automatization level and industrial robots could not replace yet the human interaction with the machine which is decisive in this trade. The methodology is based only on literature review because the concepts and academic contributions are still new and subjected to empirical trials.

Practical implication

The Industry 4.0 factors are treated as facilities to become the opportunity for organisations growing towards the race for competitive advantage. The people shall develop their practical skills with the support of facilities provided by Industry 4.0 main technical factors. The measuring tools of competencies mix model propose specific targets which could be comprehended by all categories of human factors from managerial level to practical execution.

The research approach a field less explored, but representative for the manufacturing industry which at the end is the engine for society progress and existence. Therefore, the concern shall be focused on creating the attractivity for practical work with the adapted competencies and stimulation & rewarding system for human capital.

Conclusions

For social & human sciences is unfolding directions of performance research and concepts looking for updated incentive factors to motivate and attract the human resources for manufacturing industry. Industry 4.0 factors can be a source of learning, in order to obtain the mix of competences adapted to the manufacturing industry.

Increasing the individual and team performance of employees is based on the development of the 4.0-5.0 competences mix, developing the concept of mass customization at the level of incentive factors which stimulate the contribution of each employee through their particular skills and developed knowledge.

Thus, Industry 4.0 factors could become the opportunity to grow the organisation into the race for competitive advantage. The work experience of enterprises which succeeded to survive during the pandemic crisis shall be used as best practices, to build new direction of human performance researches, available for broad spectrum of industrial activities, not only in the IT industry niche.

Table no.4- Measuring the competences level of an operator =specialist 14.0. multiskilled -upon an quantitative and qualitative evaluation

Competencies employee 4.0:		Competencies measuring by results (quantitative evaluation)	Competencies measuring by work behaviours (qualitative evaluation)	Competencies measuring by work behaviours (qualitative evaluation)	Competencies measuring by work behaviours (qualitative evaluation)
Multiskilled: able to replace other co-workers, unblock bottle necks on the working flow	Scale measuring the cumulative competences for reward system: 1-5 (1-minim,5-maximum)	Productivity (80-85 % after a month):5 (70-79 % after a month):4 (60-69 % after a month):3 (51-59 % after a month):2 (50% after a month):1	Absenteeism level/ .monthly (>5 %):5 (>10 %):4 (>15 %):3 (>20%):2 (25%):1	Fast comprehension of machine programming, handling tips(within a week) :5	Output quality level of reworks >2%-5 >3%-4 >4%-3 >5%-2 >5.5%-1
Operator=specialist 4.0				Capability of improvement for working method/ organizing the work station(within a month):5	
Essential for production: PA2: Versatility+precision	5				
Essential I5.0(5C): Abilities to work physically and pschologically safely with new tehcnology	5				
General I.4.0(8A): Ability to handle increasing complexity of simultaneous and various tasks	5				
General I.4.0(9C): Effective communication skills with the team and other entities of AI,IT	5				
General I.4.(10C): Open mindedness toward constant change.,knowledge transfer from other domains	5				

Table no.5- Measuring the competences level of an operator =specialist I4.0. trained on automated equipment –upon an quantitative and qualitative evaluation.

Competencies employee 4.0: Operation of assembly by automating sewing equipment		Competencies measuring by results (quantitative evaluation)	Competencies measuring by work behaviours (qualitative evaluation)	Competencies measuring by results (quantitative evaluation)	Competencies measuring by work behaviours (qualitative evaluation)	Competencies measuring by work behaviours (qualitative evaluation)
Denumirea competentelor Operator 4.0	Scale measuring the cumulative competences for reward system: 1-5 (1-minim,5-maximum)	Productivity (80-85 % after a month):5 (70-79 % after a month):4 (60-69 % after a month):3 (51-59 % after a month):2 (50% after a month):1	Fast comprehension of machine programming, handling tips(within a week) :5	Absenteeism level/ .monthly (> 5 %):5 (> 10 %):4 (> 15 %):3 (> 20 %):2 (25%):1	Capability of improvement for working method/ organizing the work station(within a month):5	Output quality level of reworks >2%-5 >3%-4 >4%-3 >5%-2 >5.5%-1
Essential for production: PA1: Abilities of precision +speed: 5						
Essential I5.0(5C): Abilities to work physically and psichologically safely with new technology 5						
General I.4.0(8A): Ability to handle increasing complexity of simultaneous and various tasks 3						
General I.4.0(9C): Effective communication skills with the team and other entites of AI,IT 5						
General I.4.(10C): Open mindness toward constant change.,knowledge transfer from other domains 1						

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